

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

NextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Metabolomics

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European Life Sciences Infrastructure for Biological Information

www.elixir-europe.org

My Metabolomics Story

- I started in metabolomics field in 2009 at MIT in Stephanopoulos' Lab.
- Between 2009 and 2011 followed by my tutor Christian Metallo , I start to love metabolomics world.
- In 2014, thanks to Lilia Alberghina and Greg Stephanopoulos, we create Metabolomics facility into ISBE Joint Research Unit.

ISBE Metabolomics Facility Background

ISBE.IT: a Joint Research Unit between CNR and Milano-Bicocca University that deeply believed in Systems Biology approach
“*Systems biology...is about putting together rather than taking apart, integration rather than reduction*”.

Metabolomics Facility :

- ❑ Gas Chromatography and Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometer Systems
- ❑ Integration of untargeted, targeted, targeted labeling analysis ad metabolic flux analysis
- ❑ Several Protocols, methods and homemade library

Different areas of application such as: Clinical Oncology, Neurodegeneration, Food&Nutrition, Biodiversity, Environmental Health and Toxicology

By - *ELIXIRxNextGenerationIT: Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure for Omics Data and Bioinformatics*”
(ElixirxNextGenIT)

Elixir Italy has included ISBE-IT, JRU with its know-how and its activities oriented in Systems Metabolomics and Systems Biology and we will perform the upgrade of metabolomics platform with more innovative technological systems.

LC/MS Ion Mobility

LC/MS QQQ

Rome, November 28th

Today

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II Edition of Elixir Metabolomics Workshop

Metabolomics Approaches for 'One Health'

Milan, May 30th-31st, 2024

Location: Milano Bicocca

Thanks For Your Attention

